

Cultural Mediation: Challenges of Stylistic Translation in the Francophone African Novel

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ABSTRACT

In the current thesis, I investigate how translation addresses authorial style and what distinct translational practices of meaning-making are revealed by a focus on style. African literature often employs linguistically and socioculturally nuanced stylistic figures within Western languages, like French and English (among others). This poses certain difficulties in the translation process. This research focuses on identifying and analyzing stylistic elements of selected Francophone African texts in relation to their English translations, examining the cultural and linguistic challenges encountered by the translator and how these issues are creatively handled, and exploring the target text's implications for its intended readership. The study draws on excerpts chosen from the translations of *Une si longue lettre* by Mariama Bâ and *L'Aventure ambiguë* by Cheikh Kane and their source texts to examine the original authors' stylistic choices. The research employs the theoretical frameworks of Gideon Toury's Descriptive Translation Studies and the Manipulation Theory of Susan Bassnett and André Lefevere as bases to formulate a more nuanced theoretical framework for analyzing style within the context of translation: the Stylistic-Semantic Translation Model. The data will be subjected to qualitative analysis, which will demonstrate the challenges faced by translators in adapting the styles of Francophone African novelists, including the use of culture-bound terms, repetition patterns, musical/rhythmic effects, gender-specific language, and punctuation. The study proposes strategies for more effective cultural mediation of aesthetics in Francophone African novels. Overall, this research focuses on an optimistic view of translation: first, there is a possibility of apprehending the meaningfulness and intentionality of an authorial style, and secondly, there is a possibility of communicating the latter to an audience that may be culturally, linguistically, and historically distant from the author.

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INTRODUCTION

In the current study, I propose an analysis of style in literary translation, a branch of translation that involves aesthetic texts like novels. I take the author's style to be a defining component of such texts. The author reveals values, identities, emotions, personalities, feelings, and ideas inherent in his or her cultural background and expresses them in specific, unique ways. Translating, therefore, both the *what* and *how* of an author's message, according to Nigerian translation studies scholar Damola Adeyefa, enhances the progress, development, and sustenance of the source culture by rendering it (more) visible to other communities ("Translation" 54). The question necessarily arises of whether the translator, as an individual with their own values and identities, has a style, too. This thesis intervenes in these debates to support the position that translation studies must take the style of the translator into account in considering questions of his or her presence or absence in a text. If a text is to be understood in detail, it matters both what the author says and how they say it. And traditionally, the translator is considered an invisible agent, expected to be faithful while reproducing the source text's style. However, as this research progresses, I will be defending a view that translation is a dynamic form of cultural mediation in which the translator's style or presence is significant.

To grasp the full message contained in the literary text, in the context of translation, requires paying attention to its stylistic figures. In her *Stylistic Approach to Translation*, Jean Boase-Beier emphasizes that a text cannot be understood to the fullest in translation studies unless the reader pays "attention to the style of the text: what is unique to the text and its choices, patterns in the text, and the essential nature and function of the text" (1). Therefore, stylistics contributes to the systematic close reading of a text as it provides a "helpful toolkit and checklists" and the structure of linguistic and cultural elements that can help the reader to comprehend the author's

act and art in a given text (Jinfang et al. 125). As a domain concerned with the systematic study of style, stylistics aims at interpreting the main linguistic features that are conveyed “in words, phrases, clauses, sentences, paragraphs, as well as the intentional meaning of a text” (Adeyefa, “Translation” 55).

More than just being mutually beneficial, stylistics and translation are interdependent. However, Linda Pillière finds the question of style more challenging within the context of translation (225) because style is linked to an individual author’s background, and the publisher can potentially influence the author’s style at the moment of publication. As a result, studies began to show how more scholarly attention is being drawn to explore the significance and the place of style within translation studies (Marpaung et al. 20).

This study focuses on translation as the search for a natural equivalence between source and target languages that accounts for meaning and style. The natural equivalence goes beyond the notion of mere, literal translation by prioritizing the significance of cultural contexts. It points at the work that the mediator must do, seeking and choosing the closest match in the intended language and community’s context that carries both the semantic and stylistic implications of the original text. Translation thus represents the possibility of effective human communication, cultural adequation, and mutual understanding. The search for optimistic possibilities in translation is based on Eugene Nida and Charles Taber’s perspective on equivalence in relation to identity as the criteria for producing effective translations (12), privileging the transmission of message—its meaning, style and form—while showing that form and style are essential to understanding both the meaning of the original and the translation’s effect on the intended audience; implying that, beyond conveying the meaning of the message in an original language to a target reader, attention should be paid to the source text’s style; therefore, both the meaning and the style are pertinent in the

translation process. However, according to prior studies, accurate conveyance of the voice, sense, and style of an original writer to a target audience is a delicate task; therefore, the translator will inevitably modify the voice of the original author if they do not take the stylistic elements of the source text into account during the translation process (Jinfang et al. 125).

One concern of stylistic analysis is understanding how the original author created an effect. And, rephrasing the text to understand its effect results in the notion of “translation as a form of rewriting” (Pillière 225). Previous studies argue that both the precision and the quality of the product are significantly influenced by the stylistic variations in translations (Jinfang et al. 125). This could be evident in literary translation, which creates an interface between the style of the writer and that of the mediator through cultural nuances and aesthetics. Since individuals are never the same, the style of one author is different from another’s. Likewise, languages with their contexts are diverse: for example, this difference cuts across vocabulary use, meaning, sentence structure, and pragmatics.

What is the mediator’s role in the interface between texts, languages, and cultures? More specifically, does the translator have a style that plays into this interface? It is complicated for scholars to explore the translator’s style because there is an ethical stake in the translator’s approach to authorial style. For Radwa Kotait, the translator’s style consists of subconscious choices peculiar to his or her writing, not dictated by the original or the newly created text (238). The style of the translator is therefore an obstacle to be overcome. For Radwa Kotait, attempting to strike a balance between his or her style and that of the source text’s writer, the mediator should only “reproduce as closely as possible the style of the original,” and even the “voice, subjectivity, visibility, thumbprint, and fingerprint” of the translator should not be traceable in the product (238). This brings about, therefore, a focus on producing a good translation, and the translator’s

interventions are not fixed: they continually revisit, interpret, and negotiate the text, style, meaning, and cultural contexts.

The notion of faithfulness has to do with the translator's ability to remain true to the original author's message and style. Being faithful, therefore, to the source text while reproducing its natural equivalence probably makes it more complicated for scholars to investigate the style of the mediator. This could be because the latter is viewed as subconscious choices made by the translator, and such choices and patterns are only peculiar to his or her writing—the translator's style is neither dictated by the source nor the target text (238).

I contend that attention to the translator's style is necessary for translating authorial style. This principle is important to the African novel, as studied in the present thesis, because style is a unique feature in the literary work, which is sometimes either oversimplified or misrendered in translation. The style risks being compromised during the translation and often moves African literature out of its original context into a global setting. There is greater deviation from, or even deformation of, the source text if the style is not considered during translation. Already, existing studies conclude that there is no perfect translation anywhere: the translator's aim, therefore, should be to improve the product; ignoring the original author's style will not translate better. And translating how a message is conveyed will not move the product farther from the source culture or language.

In the current study, I investigate the challenges related to translating the styles of Francophone African writers. This is a stylistic investigation of selected Francophone African novels and their English translations, with a view to identifying and exploring cultural and linguistic challenges encountered by the translators, providing certain solutions for those obstacles,

while formulating a theoretical framework that aims towards a holistic analysis of the authorial style in a translational context. My aims in this research are to:

1. Identify and compare specific stylistic figures in selected Francophone novels and their English translations.
2. Explore the cultural and linguistic issues surrounding the translation of the identified stylistic figures.
3. Identify the translation strategies employed by the translators to negotiate cultural and linguistic challenges in the target language.
4. Discuss the implications of the translators' choices for the target audience.

The study draws selected excerpts from the translations of Cheikh Kane's *L'Aventure ambiguë* (1961) and Mariama Bâ's *Une si longue lettre* (1980) and their source texts to examine the original authors' stylistic choices. The two novels were not chosen based on a comparative point of view: they were used as complementary source texts for the selected excerpts. This is with a view to making the findings more generalized within the context of Francophone African literary texts.

Mariama Bâ and Cheikh Kane are known for their distinctive styles, which are influenced by their backgrounds, displayed throughout their manner of language use. Stylistic figures such as culture-bound terms, repetition patterns, musical/rhythmic effects, gender-specific languages, and punctuation are frequently found in the different texts written by these authors, as is common in almost all African literary works. The texts of Mariama Bâ and Cheikh Kane were chosen due to their multiple translations. Also, their versions have been critically received in many languages. As a result, insights from their translations can inform general discourse and questions relating to translating Francophone African texts. Both novels are culturally significant, enriched with several

themes that provide a context for analyzing how stylistic features rooted in Francophone African culture can be found or lost in the translation process.

In addition to their themes, both novels are literarily and culturally rich, with similar, creative narrative techniques. They are generally viewed as commentaries on the society and politics of their epoch. Offering critiques of colonial influence, the novels endorse social justice and advocate for change. Through their novels, Mariama Bâ and Cheikh Kane present regular, fundamental Francophone African novelists' styles, such as (but not limited to) the use of culture-bound terms, repetition patterns, musical/rhythmic effects, gender-specific languages, and punctuation. These elements of style, however, present challenging choices for the translator, as each style seems to have more than just one possible interpretation during the translation. Therefore, there is a need to interrogate these challenges and explore possibilities for a good translation of the styles that enrich the African texts.

In the first section, I will discuss literary translation as a bridge between different cultures and languages, drawing on existing research on translation, revisiting the history and theory of translation studies in relation to African literature, and how stylistic translation began to take shape with African literature. In this context, I will develop a robust definition of style (as a distinctive, creative mode of expression that conveys the author's cultural identity) and discuss the issues around the translator's relationship to style, normative and practical constraints on the creation of the African works, and the production of translations of African literature. Then I will discuss the concept of the translator's role in mediating cultures. I will conclude this section with a review of some pertinent literature, covering the concept of stylistics and translation, the relationship between both fields, and approaches and challenges of translating style in African texts.

In the second section, I will discuss the theories and methodology of the research. The study builds on established theoretical frameworks such as Gideon Toury's Descriptive Translation Studies (Tanyitiku 7) and the Manipulation Theory of Susan Bassnett and André Lefevere (1990) to create a more effective model for analyzing styles in a translational context: a bi-layered Stylistic-Semantic Translation Model. The data will be subjected to qualitative analysis, using the newly formulated framework.

The third section presents the selected authors and their respective texts: Mariama Bâ with her *Une si longue lettre*, and Cheikh Kane with his *L'aventure Ambiguë*. I shall give a brief overview of the novelists and then mention the translators' relationships to their respective source text authors.

Lastly, I will go into the analysis proper: I will identify and compare the selected stylistic elements with their English translations, examine the cultural and linguistic issues around their translations, identify the translation strategies employed by the translators (Ferreira and Schwieter 233), and then discuss the translational implications of choices. Finally, I will conclude the findings and recommend possible solutions to facilitate the translation of Francophone African writers' style into another language.

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